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The Impact of Improved Technology of Water Harvesting Techniques, High Quality Seeds and Improved Variety in Crop Productivity and Income Generated In North Kordofan State, Sudan

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ABSTRACT

The current study was conducted in North Kordofan State, covering Sheikan, Um Rawaba and El Rahad localities during the period of 2022 - 2024. The main objective of this study was to assess the impact of water harvesting techniques, high quality seeds and improved varieties on crops productivities in traditional farming system North Kordofan State. Primary data were collected using household questionnaire. 434 households were selected from twelve villages representing the study area. A multi-stage cluster random sampling technique was used to select targeted sample. Comparisons of means, analysis of variance and descriptive statistics were used in data analysis. Both EXCEL and SPSS analytical tools were used. The study findings confirmed that practices of improved technologies contributed positively in crop productivity. Sorghum yield with improved technologies increased by 565% from yield gained without improved technologies, groundnut and sesame increased by 234% and 184% respectively. The study results indicated that groundnut recorded the highest revenue followed by sorghum, while sesame recorded the lowest one. The study conclude that the use of improved technologies of water harvesting techniques, high quality seeds and improved variety have appositve impact on crop productivities then the study recommended that improved technologies and services should be made readily available and accessible to producers in time and at affordable price. Means of production should be avail and accessible to producers.

Keywords: smallholder farmers, traditional rain-fed farming system, North Kordofan State

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the declaration of secession of South Sudan on 2011, the geography, demography, and the economy of Sudan underwent structural changes. The neighboring countries were reduced from 9 to 7; total area was reduced to 75% (from 2.5 to 1.9 million km²).The population is down to 79% from (42 to 33 million). The arable agricultural land is representing 78% of the historical arable land of the unified Sudan (175 million feddans). The livestock population is estimated at 120 million heads representing 72% of the historical numbers. Range resources and forest cover reduced to only 65% of the historical resources. The major agro-ecological change is that 90% of the Sudan land area is now classified as arid-land (IFAD, IAMDP, project design report, 2017).The agricultural sector is the most important economic sector in the country; it contributes about 43% of the country Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The sector

provides employment for more than 70% of the population and provides inputs to many major manufacturing industries. Agriculture is the key sector for poverty reduction and food security, for fueling growth and replacing oil as the key engine of the economy. The Agriculture Revival Programme (ARP) aimed to increased agricultural exports and decreased reliance on oil exports through increased productivity, improved food security and agricultural incomes, reduced rural poverty and redressed regional imbalances.(ARP pepper, 2017).Agriculture is the largest production sector, which provides livelihood for 75% of the population, and contributes around 90% of export earning if oil contribution is not considered (Seirab, 2005). This sector has two main sub-sectors, irrigated sub-sector in the central clay plain and rain-fed sub-sector in the northern part of the country (Suliman , 2005). The rain-fed production system is an important agricultural subsector, typically divided into semi-mechanized farming, traditional crop production and livestock systems. Depending on rainfall, the rain-fed subsectors contributed three-quarters of foreign exchange earnings from agricultural exports (Seirab, 2005). Traditional rain-fed farming is practiced by family households with farms ranging from 2 to 50 hectares in size, farming for income and subsistence (FAO, 2021). Traditional rain-fed farming covers about 18 million feddans, growing about 95 percent of the country's millet, 38 percent of sorghum, 67 percent of groundnut and 38 percent of sesame. The subsector also grows gum Arabic, rosella and melon seeds for export. Semi-mechanized rain-fed farming is practiced by large farmers and companies with low rent leases granted by the federal government and produces 40 percent of the country's sorghum, 62 percent of sesame and 90 percent of sunflower and cotton grown in the country (IFAD, IAMDP, project design report, 2017).

Sorghum is an important staple food crop that along with sesame and groundnut represents important sources of income for many rural households in Sudan and Kordofan region. Since these crops have a great influence on farm economy it is important to increase and maintain high yields to defeat food insecurity/ poverty and to improve the rural farmers' economic situation. Many governmental, non-governmental (NGO) initiatives have been launched; one goal has been to increase yields with the help of agricultural improve technologies such as water harvesting techniques, improved seeds and new varieties. Another part of the challenge has been to raise awareness on different farming techniques, and to provide information on how to increase yields. (IFAD, 2017).During the last decades North Kordofan State has experienced huge variations in the environmental conditions- drought, desertification and instability of rainfall - are the major environmental troubles, these symptoms have a major influence and effect on the economic activities, crop production, poverty and food security. North Kordofan State faces a number of problems which are the result of combination constraints such as environmental, economic, resources, marketing, inputs and political factors. In North Kordofan State, Sorghum and Millet are an important staple food crops while Sesame and Groundnut representing main cash crops. Since these crops have a great influence on farm economy it is important to increase and maintain high yields.According to a higher yield enables farmers to sell parts of their harvest, which in the long run makes it possible to improve their financial situation (Emana et al., 2010). To reach a more stable economy, country wise and for the individual farmers, it is essential to increase the yield of produced crops. This study's main goal is to assess the impact of the contribution of water harvesting techniques, high quality seeds and improved variety in crop productivity and household income.

2. STUDY AREA AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study area

The study area covers North Kordofan State, which includes: Sheikan, Um Rawaba and Rahad localities. The area in general is subjected to further degradation due to hardship environmental condition, climatic instability, desert moving to the south, recurrent drought, cutting down of trees for various uses, over cultivation and over grazing. The area of North Kordofan is estimated to be 195,280 km² of which approximately 45 million feddans is suitable for agriculture and forestry activities. The main problems facing agriculture in state are the unfortunate climate and the low rainfalls. The soils in generally are sandy soil in the northern parts of the state interested with some clay soil and the valleys and oasis; the

central parts of the state are clayed Pedi plains to clay plains. In the southern parts of it, soils are moderately fertile but are good for the majority of the dry lands' crops. The main crops grown in the state according to the availability of water are millet, sorghum, sesame, groundnuts, watermelons and Roselle. Sometimes field crops are mixed with some local variety of beans (MoP&ERs, 2024).Awouda,(1996) reported that, the vegetation growth is affected by the amount of rainfall and the type of soil. In the northern parts of the State, where rainfall is relatively low, there are scattered shrubs and low grasses. In drier parts *Acacia tortilis*, *Lepladenia pyrotechnic*, *Moeura crassifolia*, *Acacia albida* and *Acacia senegal*. Towards its wetter edge area, *Combretum glutinosum*, *Guiera senegalens* alternate with *Acacia Senegal* were the main type of vegetation cover.

2.2 Research Methodology

2.2.1 Data sources

Both primary and secondary data will be used, primary data collect through designed questionnaire which consist of three sections, the first section to gain data regarding household income and expenditure, the second section is individual questionnaire to collect data regarding farm budget model, the third section to collect data regarding improved technology adoption rate, while secondary data depend on published & unpublished books, reports and articles from IFAD, FAO and other related institutions websites. The study depends on database that collected by Seed Development Project (SDP) and Integrated Agricultural and Marketing Development Project (IAMDP) that funded by IFAD.

2.2.2 Sampling and Sample Frame

A sample frame will be developed from existing records and database at the Seed Development Project (SDP) and Integrated Agricultural and Marketing Development Project (IAMDP) that project co-financed by IFAD and Sudan government and used to accomplish random selection.

Multi-stage cluster random sample system will be used to identify the sites and respondents from the three determine localities of North Kordofan State. In the first stage was selected three localities out of eight (37.5%). Second stage 45% of targeted communities were selected randomly 12 communities out of 27, while 10% of the targeted beneficiaries were randomly selected as the third stage.

2.2.3 Sample size

434 households were selected randomly from 4340 households that equaled 10% from total population that served by Integrated Agricultural and Marketing Development Project (IAMDP) that funded by IFAD and government of Sudan and State Ministry of Production and Economic Resources in North Kordofan State as leads agency. The IAMDP targeted 27 communities from three targeted localities and 12 of them were selected from a total (45%), giving a total of 434 selected household for the study area and selected 8-12 households from each community, this due to homogeneity of household potentiality in the selected community.

Distribution of population and sample size

Locality	Population		Sample	
	Communities	Households	Communities	Households
Sheikan	9	1387	4	145
El Rahad	9	1230	4	114
Um Rawaba	9	1723	4	175
Total	27	4340	12	434

2.2.4 Analytical Frame of work

Comparisons of means, analysis of variance and descriptive statistics were used. Both EXCEL and SPSS analytical tools were used in data analysis.

Regarding to main study objective that stated as “to assess the impact of the contribution of water harvesting techniques, high quality seeds and improved variety in crop productivity and household income” was overcome through the following formula

$$\text{Formula (1)} \ Y = P/A$$

Where (Y) stand for yield in kg/feddan and (P) total production in kg and (A) stand for area under cultivation per feddan

$$\text{Formula (2)} \ M = \Sigma X/N$$

Where (M) stand for means (X) stand for cases (N) stand for number of cases

To see the distribution of the collected data the standard deviation (s) was calculated according to the following formula

$$\text{Formula (4)}$$

$$STD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n}}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study found that the average area cultivated by sorghum were 4.3 feddan per household in each. while the sesame and groundnut average cultivated area were 4 and 2.6 feddans respectively. The total area under cultivation were 10.9 feddans in average to each household in the study area these situation assure that the small farmers in traditional rain fed defined as the family that cultivated below 15 feddans (6 hectares) as stated by IFAD in the project document regarding integrated agricultural and marketing development project (IFAD, IAMDP, 2017).

3.1 Crop yield and improved technology

Table (1) showed that the average production of sorghum was 1314 kilogram while average production for sesame and groundnut were 365 and 1094 kilograms respectively. These results revealed that the yield of the different crops of sorghum, sesame and groundnut were 306, 91 and 421 kg/feddan respectively as shown in Table (1). The sorghum yield increased from 46 to 309 kg/fed when they used improved technologies which was increased by 565%, sesame increased by 184% and groundnut increased by 234%, highest yield increment was reported in sorghum crop followed by groundnut while the sesame reported the lowest increment in yield. These results illustrated that sorghum crop was highly responded to improved technologies of water harvesting techniques, improved variety and high quality seeds compared to groundnut while sesame crop was the lowest response, IFAD Seeds Development Project (SDP) found the same results in 2015 also ARS Elobied station stated that sorghum is highly significant to improved variety and water harvesting activities. The study found that sesame was the lowest response to the improved technologies when compared with sorghum and groundnut.

3.2 Crop yield comparison

Figure (1) showed productivity of main crops (sorghum, sesame and groundnut) in the study area using improved technologies of water harvesting techniques, improved variety and high quality seeds compared to without using improved technologies (control), long-term average yield in North Kordofan state, national and international yield of main crops. The figure cited from North Kordofan ARS station (2015) and study findings. In this respect, sorghum yield with improved technologies increased by 565% from sorghum yield without using improved technologies, and increased by 456% of North Kordofan long-term average yield and increased by only 5% of national sorghum yield. While decreased by 46% from

international sorghum average yield. Sesame average yield with improved technologies increased by 184% of without improved technologies and by 60% of North Kordofan long-term average and by 20% from national yield while it declined by 58% from international sesame average yield. Groundnut yield with improved technologies was increased by 236%, 192%, 17% and 5% from without improved technologies, North Kordofan long-term average, national and international groundnut average yield. Study demonstrated an increase yield of all crops when practices improved technologies in comparing with non-used of improved technologies, North Kordofan and national average yield of sorghum, sesame and groundnut, while yield declined when compared with international average yield accept groundnut which reported increasing. These results confirmed that practices improved technologies of water harvesting techniques; high quality seeds and improved variety contribute positively in crop productivity.

Table (1) Descriptive of productivity kg/feddans by crop

	Sorghum	Sesame	Groundnut
Area cultivated in feddans	4.3	4.0	2.6
Production in kg per feddan	1314	365	1094
Yield in kg/feddan with technologies	306	91	421
Yield without technologies	46	32	125
Increasing percent	565%	184%	234%

Sources: Survey data, 2023

Figure (1) productivity of crops in comparing to with, without improved, long-term average, national and international yield

3.3 The impact of improved technologies in income generation and economic situation

As stated before farm income contributes around 66.5% from the total family income, which confirmed that farm income representing the main sources of family income in study area. The empirical data analysis reveals that crop production shared by 66% of the farm income and 43% of the total family income which confirmed that crop production revenue represent the most important sources of total family income in the study area.

3.3.1 Crop production revenue:

Table (2) shows average cultivated area, crop production revenue for sorghum, sesame and groundnut crops in North Kordofan state, the household average cultivated area around 10.9 feddans that consist of sorghum 4.3 feddans (39%), 4.0 feddans for sesame (37%) while 2.6 feddan (24%) devoted to groundnut crop. Other crops were cultivated as minor crops, cultivated by intercropping system or within the main crop and its impact on revenue is minor accordingly the study neglected it and depend on main crops of sorghum, sesame and groundnut.

Sorghum and sesame exhibit lower yield per unit area compared to groundnut, which demonstrates the highest yield per feddan. However, the farm revenue from groundnut is also the highest, indicating its economic advantage despite higher input costs. Residual values from farm products significantly contribute to total revenue, particularly in groundnut (15%), where the value of farm residuals is the highest. The residuals' role in enhancing overall farm income suggests that farmers benefit not only from crop sales but also from by-products, which are essential in traditional rain fed farming systems.

Groundnut is the most profitable crop due to its high yield, high revenue, and significant residual value revenue. Sorghum remains a strong performer, likely due to its high area cultivated and stable productivity. Sesame's lower revenue suggests constraints in productivity and efficiency, despite its high market price.

3.3.2 Cost of production

The cost of production in traditional rain fed cultivation sector encompasses with many challenges, Table (3) shows twelve items or cultivation practices starting from land renting land clearance up to harvesting cost. Land renting is only applicable for sorghum and sesame, with an average cost of 2.309 SDG. Seed cost is notably high for groundnut, reflecting its intensive input requirement. Similarly, tillage costs represent a significant portion of the total production cost, indicating the importance of land preparation in rain-fed agriculture and uses of water harvesting practices for all crops. Family labour and weeding contribute substantially to total production expenses and is highest for groundnut, suggesting a higher dependency on unpaid labour. The use of *Nafeer* labour (a traditional collective labour system) is observed in all crops, but is more significant in groundnut, potentially due to its higher labour demand for specific operations.

Table (2) Total crop revenue /SDG in North Kordofan state

Descriptive Statistics	Revenue	Percent
Sorghum		
Average cultivated area (feddan)	4.3	
Crop revenue (SDG)	335,023	90.2
Farm residual revenue (SDG)	36,339	9.8
Total revenue (SDG)	371,362	
Revenue per feddan (SDG)	77,912	
Sesame		
Average cultivated area (feddan)	4.0	
Crop revenue (SDG)	206,401	93.4
Farm residual revenue (SDG)	14,552	6.6
Total revenue (SDG)	220,953	
Revenue per feddan (SDG)	55,238	
Groundnut		
Average cultivated area (feddan)	2.6	
Crop revenue (SDG)	386,528	85.0
Farm residual revenue (SDG)	67,536	15.0
Total revenue (SDG)	454,064	
Revenue per feddan (SDG)	174,640	

Sources: Survey data, 2023

Table (3) Cost of production in study area of North Kordofan

Practice	Crop			SE±
	Sorghum	Sesame	Groundnut	
Land renting cost	2,309	2,309	0	1.089ns
Land clearance cost	3,963.0	3,252.4	2,650.5	301.9ns
Seed cost	5,139.8	8,618.1	46,474.6	878.5ns
Seed dressing cost	958.78	269.28	1,862.82	70.1 **
Pest control cost	142.52	927.27	122.66	35.31**
Tillage cost	40,744.2	39,298	24,569.1	1,534**
Herbicide cost	6,401.16	2,902.3	3,697.67	674.6ns
Sowing cost	3,708.35	3,811.8	17,455.9	635.3**
Weeding cost	7,552.54	10,276	17,408.3	874.4**
Harvesting cost	23,825.2	22,959	18,891.57	1635**
Family Labour cost	33,858.8	33,833	46,774.7	1,412**
Nafeer Labour cost	1,339.03	1,729.0	4,974.65	375.9**
	129,942	130,185	166,010	

Sources: Survey data, 2023

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that Improved technologies usage in comparing to without, long-term average yield in North Kordofan state, national and international yield of main crops. Study revealed that an increase in yield of all crops when practices improved technologies when compared with non-used of improved technologies, North Kordofan and national average yield of sorghum, sesame and groundnut, while yield declined when compared with international average yield except groundnut which reported increment. These results confirmed that practices improved technologies of water harvesting techniques; high quality seeds and improved variety contribute positively in crop productivity.

The study designed the following recommendations

- Recommended improved technologies and services should be made readily available and accessible to producers in time and at affordable price.
- Means of production should be avail and accessible to producers in order to make use of improved technologies such as suitable hand tools, intermediate technology tools and mechanization equipments

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